

CONTEMPORARY RADIO TRENDS. OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES IN THE NEW AUDIO LANDSCAPE

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Abstract

Despite the rapid rise of digital platforms, streaming services, and social media, radio has maintained its relevance as a medium of communication and entertainment. This popular medium has adapted to the evolution of technology and the profound changes in consumer preferences by embracing the new trends that have reshaped the means of delivery and the modalities of content creation. Some of the most important contemporary trends in radio presented in this article are podcasts and on-demand content, digital streaming, social media engagement, the growing focus on niche content and the interactive mobile applications.

Keywords: radio, podcast, social media, digital streaming, trends

One of the world's oldest mass communication mediums has experienced a spectacular transformation in the contemporary digital landscape. Blending the essential principles and traditions with the state-of-the-art technology, radio has been continuously adapting to the changes of media paradigm, avoiding the fading into obsolescence. The modern listeners demand personalization, accessibility, and interactivity and the radio stations all over the world rely on digital, satellite, and internet-based formats, offering a more diverse and interactive listening experience than ever before. In a successful attempt to maintain its relevance and popularity, radio has embraced all the new technological advancements, as the vice president (Music) of Saregama India, Kartik Kalla, writes: "The radio industry has consistently adapted to the latest developments led by content and technology, thereby cementing its continued presence and prosperity. Radio is a highly efficient medium for disseminating information because its communication practically reaches a comprehensive set of audience. Radio has an inherent ability to connect with its listeners on a personal level while simultaneously

engaging a large base of audience via its medium. It has intangible benefits over other mediums in terms of portability, affordability, and accessibility. Radio has developed into a progressive medium that sets the pace for technological advancements within the broadcasting sector. Not only does it help educate the masses, but it also brings attention to the need for social change, fosters curiosity, and empowers individuals to take action. It enlightens and broadens the public's horizons, causing a shift in how people perceive their surroundings"¹.

On-demand audio content has become almost compulsory worldwide and one of the most significant trends in radio is the impressive rise of podcasting, a phenomenon that has grown from a tiny market niche into a major form of media. Podcasts are audio programs made available for on-demand listening, distributed on the websites of the radio stations or on online platforms like Spotify, Apple Podcasts, and Google Podcasts. Compared to traditional live radio, podcasts offer more flexibility, allowing listeners to access content at their leisure. The development of podcasting has been caused by several factors, but one of the most important, if not the most, is that on-demand content allows for time-shifted listening, offering an advantage over the real-time broadcasts provided by traditional radio.

The lockdown periods of time during the Covid pandemic made many people turn to the on-demand audio content distributed on the Internet, therefore 2021 saw a spectacular increase of podcast consumption all over the world, including Great Britain, as emphasized by several studies on media market: "2021 saw an uptick in podcast listenership of public radio broadcasters as well as a heightened focus on increasing podcast content. In December, the BBC said podcast listening via its BBC Sounds platform rose by nearly 25% from January to November 2021. According to the BBC, there were 558 million plays of podcasts and on-demand radio programmes on BBC Sounds in the UK in 2021. Overall, the broadcaster recorded 1.3 billion plays of music, radio, and podcast – an increase of 8% compared to the same period in 2020"². This positive trend was also emphasized by Jonathan Wall, controller of BBC Sounds: "Listening to podcasts and music mixes has really grown again this year, with new music and podcast tabs on BBC Sounds making it even easier for listeners to find audio to suit what they're looking for. It's great to

¹ Kartik Kalla, *Key Drivers of Radio: The Market Trends and Digital Tools*, <https://www.financialexpress.com/business/brandwagon-key-drivers-of-radio-the-market-trends-and-digital-tools-2962930/>

² <https://www.publicmediaalliance.org/five-public-media-audio-trends-to-keep-an-eye-on-in-2022/>

see our firm favourites and brilliant big name talent continuing to delight the audience, as well as new titles prove to be really popular this year”³.

The BBC Sounds achieved a resounding success over the past few years and the professionals of UK’s public radio network did not conceal their satisfaction to providing a platform that had started to reach more and more audience, as Charlotte Moore, BBC Chief Content Officer, states: “Whilst listening habits continue to evolve, the latest quarterly figures demonstrate the power of breakfast radio, bringing people together in all four corners of the UK, with more listeners choosing to start their day with music from across the BBC’s radio networks. We want to offer audiences more choice and help them discover distinctive, high quality audio content from the BBC whenever they want to, and I’m delighted to see continued growth of BBC Sounds which has achieved a record 643 million plays of all content across radio, podcasts and music mixes. BBC Sounds has peaked at over 5 million users for the first time this quarter, which is a fantastic achievement for the platform in its 5th year. Our speech networks continue to provide listeners with top quality on-demand programming and podcasts”⁴. BBC Sounds registered a record quarter between January and March 2024, with a weekly audience of almost 5 million users across the app, website and voice activated devices and, for the first time ever, a peak of more than 5 million listeners⁵.

The Head of Broadcast and Content Production Studies at the Ariel University, Tal Laor, reviewed the way in which radio managed to adapt to the new media paradigm: “In radio, considerable effort is made to make content available to listeners on diverse platforms, creating formats such as podcasts and radio on-demand (Bonet et al., 2011; Laor, 2019a; Steinfeld and laor, 2019). The word ‘podcast’ (a combination of ‘iPod’, a brand of portable media players made by Apple, and ‘broadcast’) refers to information-based online broadcasts available for live listening or downloading at any time (Berry, 2006). Many consumers consider podcasts to be a type of radio platform because a podcast’s audio content can be listened to without reference to visuals (Punnett, 2016). The popularity of audio on-demand and podcasts is increasing steadily and many US podcasts attract more than 73 million listeners per month (Edison Research, 2018). Serial, an original podcast documenting the investigation into a murder in 1999, reached 5 million downloads, becoming the most popular

³ Ibid.

⁴ <https://www.bbc.com/mediacentre/2024/bbc-sounds-peaks-at-over-5-million-weekly-users-for-first-time-and-boost-listeners-bbc-music-breakfast-shows>

⁵ Ibid.

podcast in iTunes' history (Punnett, 2016)"⁶. Laor also stresses the advantages of radio on-demand, which allows personalized choices: "Content can be tailored to the tastes of individual listeners in a way it can't on traditional radio. Although users can connect via social media, streaming services ignore all notions of a collective and focus on the desires and interests of each individual consumer (Glantz, 2016). Research also indicates that on-demand segmental listening offers the added value of selection of specific aspects of content based on individual preferences. The division of content into segments is presented to consumers as a time-saving tool to allow listeners to focus on relevant content by filtering out irrelevant content. This concept is known as 'time squeezing', allowing the consumer to 'shrink' content in time and space and to adjust it to lifestyle preferences (Moshe, 2012). Accessibility of segments and programmes on demand encourages listeners to consume additional and new content by spillover (Moshe et al., 2017)"⁷.

Podcasting is just an element in the process of reinventing radio and this medium has turned to a niche market strategy, as professor Jarosław Kinal from the University of Rzeszow (Poland) observed in an article published in 2018 in which he described the historical background input radio format and the modern scientific definitions of the phenomenon: "Nowadays, the impact of marketing solutions for media system is particularly noticeable in case of the so-called traditional media, i.e. newspapers, radio and television. With reference to the declining expenditures and audience, publishers of these forms of media are looking for niches allowing survival. In the radio broadcasting sector, the niche is well defined target audience mentally attached to the program or Radio. In the era of market consolidation is often that a company has in its portfolio several radio stations with different target groups"⁸.

Kartik Kalla is aware of the boost radio received by adapting digital technologies as part of its continuing process of adapting to the new audio landscape, a process the media executive calls "radigitalization": "Rapid 'Radigitalization' i.e. the amalgamation of radio and digital solutions has aided the growth of our business and will continue to play a key role in heightening the audience as well as the advertiser base. Digital technologies have offered a greater proliferation for delving into tech-enabled entertainment options

⁶ Tal Laor, *Radio on Demand: New Habits of Consuming Radio Content*, Sage Journals, 2022, <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1177/17427665211073868>

⁷ Ibid.

⁸ Jarosław Kinal, *Modern Models of Radio Broadcasting as an Example of the Formatting of Emission Panels*, in *European Scientific Journal* February 2018 /SPECIAL/ edition ISSN: 1857 – 7881 (Print) e - ISSN 1857- 7431

among audiences. The radio business has been able to recreate and reimagine its terrestrial intellectual properties (IPs) on digital platforms in an efficient manner owing to the complementary nature of audio and digital solutions. The significance of AI in the digital entertainment context is also growing progressively more relevant as it is an excellent tool to push bespoke content to the audience depending on their preferences”⁹. Radio Today, a website that provides news, features, and reviews related to the radio industry in the United Kingdom, observes that the “digital shift has allowed radio to reach audiences in ways previously unimaginable”¹⁰ and reviews the most important contemporary elements of the radio landscape: digital streaming platforms, podcasts and on-demand content, interactive mobile apps, smart speaker integration, and social media engagement. Kartik Kalla lists the essential digital tools employed in today’s radio in order to support several functions such as scheduling, recording, editing, and transmitting: “Software for scheduling enables radio stations to plan and arrange their programming in advance, digital audio workstations (DAWs) is a software utilised for audio recording, editing, and production, streaming software enables radio stations to live-stream their programming over the Internet, tools for managing and scheduling postings on social media networks, as well as monitoring engagement and analytics, software for podcasting that permits radio stations to make and distribute podcasts, software utilized for scheduling and managing the music played on a radio station, and software for automation enables radio stations to automate duties such as playing pre-recorded programmes, advertisements, and music. These tools are essential for radio stations to operate more efficiently, reach a larger audience, and engage with listeners in novel ways”¹¹. The listeners engage with their favorite stations and shows in the new ways provided by the integration of social media with radio content. Twitter, Facebook, Instagram, and other social media platforms serve as efficient complementary tools for radio broadcasters in order to promote their content, engage with their audience in real-time, and creating a sense of community. Most of the radio shows encourage nowadays live interaction through social media, listeners being able to comment or vote on topics put up

⁹ Kartik Kalla, *Key Drivers of Radio: The Market Trends and Digital Tools*, <https://www.financialexpress.com/business/brandwagon-key-drivers-of-radio-the-market-trends-and-digital-tools-2962930/>

¹⁰ <https://radiotoday.co.uk/2024/07/the-evolution-of-radio-in-the-digital-age-adapting-to-new-listener-habits/>

¹¹ Kartik Kalla, *Key Drivers of Radio: The Market Trends and Digital Tools*, <https://www.financialexpress.com/business/brandwagon-key-drivers-of-radio-the-market-trends-and-digital-tools-2962930/>

for debate on air. The propagation of smart speakers such as Amazon Alexa, Google Home, and Apple's HomePod has also broadened the horizon for radio consumption. Smart speakers have revitalized this medium by facilitating the access through simple voice commands to radio stations, podcasts, and streaming services. Thus, the use of smart speakers to acquire audio content has increased dramatically recently, providing an additional platform for radio broadcasters to reach audiences in homes, offices, and anywhere else.

But this profound transformation came with a series of challenges, the most difficult one being the multitude of alternatives to be found in the digital realm, the almost infinite options that the World Wide Web provides: "Radio stations have had to adapt to new competition, not just from other audio mediums but from a myriad of digital entertainment options. This has led to innovative approaches in content creation and audience engagement"¹². The challenges ignited an explosion of creativity for the creators of radio content, both in form and substance, and what seemed to be a vital threat transformed into the dawn of a new age for this popular medium: "With the Radigitalization strategy, the intersection between radio and the digital realm is poised for a prosperous era"¹³. And the statistical data resulted from different market surveys and analysis confirm this ascending trend in 2024 not only in Europe, but also in the USA: "The total use of audio is significant - Americans spend more than four hours with audio every day - and it's important to view it from multiple lenses. Consumers give nearly 70% of their daily ad-supported audio time to radio, 20% to podcasts and the rest to streaming audio (music services) or satellite radio (select channels)"¹⁴.

The African digital station Mount FM, based in Ghana, lists on its website the key industry trends that shaped the 2024 landscape of radio broadcasting: digitalization and hybrid broadcasting, podcasting and on-demand content, personalization and AI-driven content, mobile and smart device integration, interactive and engaging content formats, monetization strategies and revenue models, local and hyper-local content, sustainability and environmental initiatives. In conclusion, the radio industry was characterized by "digitalization, content diversification, personalization, mobile integration, interactivity, innovative monetization strategies, localization, and sustainability initiatives. These industry trends reflect the

¹² <https://radiotoday.co.uk/2024/07/the-evolution-of-radio-in-the-digital-age-adapting-to-new-listener-habits/>

¹³ Kartik Kalla, *Key Drivers of Radio: The Market Trends and Digital Tools*, <https://www.financialexpress.com/business/brandwagon-key-drivers-of-radio-the-market-trends-and-digital-tools-2962930/>

¹⁴ <https://www.nielsen.com/insights/2024/nielsen-the-record-audio-listening-trends/>

dynamic nature of radio broadcasting as it continues to adapt to changing consumer preferences, technological advancements, and market dynamics. As broadcasters embrace these trends and leverage new opportunities, radio remains a resilient and influential medium in the media and entertainment landscape"¹⁵. Contemporary trends in radio reflect the adaptability of this medium in an environment influenced by the swift evolution of technology and the changing consumer behavior. The development of podcasting, digital streaming, personalized content, and niche content demonstrates radio's dynamic transformation. At the same time, trends like hyperlocalization, social responsibility, experiential marketing, and technological innovation prove how radio keeps staying relevant by enhancing its intense connection with the listeners.

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¹⁵ <https://mountfm.com/2024/03/20/industry-trends-for-radio-in-2024/>